

Effect of Load-Bypass on Structural Efficiencies of Bonded and Bolted Repairs

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SUMMARY

Low-stiffness scarf inserts within adhesively bonded scarf repairs and bolted doublers within mechanically fastened repairs transfer less load than that originally supported by the damaged area of the structure. In this work we present an improved analysis, utilising the inclusion analogy technique, to quantify the effect of load-bypass on the structural efficiency of bonded and bolted repairs.

Keywords: Composite repair, stress analysis

INTRODUCTION

Composite repairs, particularly those involving external doublers that are either adhesively bonded or mechanically fastened, tend to produce a complex stress state that differs significantly from that prevailing in the original structure. While the main function of a repair is to reduce the strength criticality of the structure by lowering stresses, the region over which the applied load transitions into the repair must be carefully designed to avoid premature failure of the adhesive bond or the parent structure at fastener locations.

In the case of adhesively bonded repairs to cracked structures, the increase in local stiffness in the repair region gives rise to a load attraction phenomenon, which was analysed by Rose [1] using Eshelby's inclusion analogy. Extensive computational analyses using the finite element (FE) method have supported the accuracy of the inclusion analogy solution [2]. For adhesively bonded scarf repairs having low-stiffness patches and bolted doubler repairs to through-thickness damage, the opposite occurs: the repair transfers less load than that being carried by the damaged area of the parent

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structure. This load-bypass phenomenon around the repair region is currently not considered in designing repairs. The purpose of the present work is to extend the inclusion analogy solution to adhesively bonded scarf repairs and bolted doubler repairs. Discussion will focus on exploiting the potential benefit of load-bypass in improving the structural efficiencies of repairs.

BONDED SCARF REPAIRS

Scarf repairs are presently designed by analysing a scarf joint representing the most highly loaded strip along the principal loading direction. In a scarf joint between dissimilar adherends, the entire applied load goes through the adhesive bond, inducing a stress concentration at the tip of the stiffer adherend [3]. As a result, the repair material should match the parent structure to achieve maximum strength.

For joints between un-matched adherends, the scarf profile can be optimised to achieve a uniform stress distribution [4]. The resulting optimum scarf profile, which differs from the conventional straight taper, would require high precision machining, which may pose a practical problem as scarfing is carried out mostly by a manual grinding operation. An alternative technique is to investigate the feasibility of deploying a low-stiffness insert, taking advantage of the load-shedding effect.

As an example of load shedding, consider the case of a circular inclusion in a plate-like host structure. Here the term inclusion refers to a circular insert that is rigidly connected to the host structure. Denoting the moduli of the inclusion and the host structure as E_i and E_s , respectively, the stress in the inclusion can be readily determined using Eshelby's inclusion analogy method. Omitting the detailed derivations, which can be found in Ref. [2], the stress in the inclusion is given by

$$\sigma_i = \frac{3E_i / E_s}{1 + 2E_i / E_s} \sigma_{applied}, \quad (1)$$

which is illustrated in Figure 1. The stress in the inclusion increases rapidly as its stiffness increases.

The results shown in Figure 1 confirm that it is possible to reduce the inclusion stress using inclusions with lower stiffness than the host structure. In a repair scenario, by deflecting the load away from a repair through the use of reduced modulus, we can lower the stress being carried by the adhesive. Provided the adjacent structure retains an adequate margin of safety, it is possible to achieve higher repair efficiencies.

The scarf angle is typically small as the shear strength of structural adhesives is much less than the strength of the composite structure. The scarf overlap represents, therefore, a large transition region over which the combined stiffness varies between that of the scarf repair and the parent structure.

Figure 1: Ratio of stresses for a circular inclusion of increasing stiffness in a host structure.

To investigate the difference between a straight-through inclusion and a scarf repair insert with small taper angles, detailed three-dimensional FE analyses were carried out, and are summarised in Figure 2. FE analyses were conducted for two different ratios of adhesive shear modulus G_a to parent modulus E_s , which were selected to represent a highly stiff almost rigid bond ($G_a/E_s = 0.1$) and a typical epoxy resin at room temperature ($G_a/E_s = 0.01$). The left image of Figure 2 shows stress in the load (x) direction for the baseline ($E_i = E_s$, $G_a/E_s = 0.01$), quarter model, where 100 MPa was applied along the right edge. The right image in Figure 2 shows FE stress results with the analytical solution for a straight circular inclusion.

Figure 2: Effect of stiffness on scarf repair stress: Left: Stress in the load (x) direction, $E_i = E_s$, $G_a/E_s = 0.01$. Right: Ratio between scarf insert and parent structure stresses.

Computational results suggest that, due to the stiffness variation over the scarf overlap region, the stress at the centre of the scarf repair is higher than the analytically predicted level for straight inclusions. An improved analytical solution was derived by assuming that the stress in the repair is constant, so the effective stiffness of the repair becomes

$$E_i = E_r \frac{(1 + 2L/D)(1 + E_r/E_s)}{1 + (1 + 4L/D)E_r/E_s}, \quad (2)$$

where L and D are the scarf length and the damage diameter, respectively, as shown in Figure 3. Predictions of the improved solution are also included in Figure 2, where it can be seen that the improved solution provides very good predictions, particularly for the typical epoxy adhesive model, and captures the increased stress in the insert.

Figure 3: Adhesive scarf repair geometry.

From these results, the peak adhesive shear stress increases nearly proportionally to the ratio between adherend stiffness for high stiffness ratios, which has been shown previously by Hart-Smith [3]. As such, small reductions in repair stiffness for a scarf joint cause a small reduction in stress due to the reduced load. However, lowering the stiffness of the scarf repair would cause a large increase in adhesive shear stress, due to the stiffness mismatch [3]. As a result, the net effect of a reduced stiffness repair is an increase in adhesive stresses. For brittle adhesives, where joint failure is largely dictated by peak stresses, this would lead to a slight reduction in joint strength. For a ductile adhesive the effect would be more complex due to adhesive plasticity, though it is likely that the joint strength would either be unchanged or slightly reduced. Advanced joint configurations achieving increased strength using reduced stiffness inserts are the focus of future work, and require optimisation of the insert to reduce stress concentrations.

BOLTED DOUBLER REPAIRS

Bolted doubler repairs are conventionally designed by analysing representative bolted joints; the repair strength is equated to the load-carrying capacity of the joint. This approach implicitly assumes that the bolted repair fully restores the stiffness of the host structure, and thus transfers the load originally supported by the damage area of the structure [5]. However, bolted joints are much more compliant than bonded joints [6] because of the deformation associated with bolt rotation and elongation of the bolt holes, especially one-sided doubler repairs in which the bolts are under single shear. Neglecting the high compliance of bolted joints may result in non-conservative designs for small damage, as the bolted doubler only attracts a small fraction of the applied load. In the following, the inclusion analogy method presented in the previous section will be extended to account for the influence of bolt joint compliance on the repair efficiency.

Experimental

Critical to the structural efficiency of one-sided bolted repairs is the flexibility of fasteners under single shear, which causes a higher degree of bolt rotation than in a double shear configuration. By modifying the double shear formula [7], Nelson *et al.* [8] proposed the following expression for the bolt flexibility, C , in single shear

$$C = \frac{2(t_s + t_d)}{3G_b A_b} + \left[\frac{2(t_s + t_d)}{t_s t_d E_{bbr}} + \frac{1}{t_s \sqrt{E_s E_{st}}} + \frac{1}{t_d \sqrt{E_d E_{dt}}} \right] (1 + 3\beta), \quad (3)$$

where: t_s and t_d are the thickness of the structure and doubler, respectively; G_b and A_b denote the shear modulus and cross-sectional area of the bolt; E_{bbr} is the bearing modulus of the bolt, which is normally equal to the bolt Young's modulus; E_s and E_{st} are the longitudinal and lateral moduli of the structure; E_d and E_{dt} are the longitudinal and lateral moduli of the doubler; and β represents the fraction of the bending moment on the bolt that is reacted by the non-uniform bearing stress across the thickness. The parameter β was suggested [8] to be approximately 0.5 for countersunk fasteners.

To verify the above expression, single-lap joints fastened with either a countersunk blind fastener (Composi-lok® II) or a conventional non-blind bolt (NAS 1204-7) were tested under tension at room temperature. Specimens were machined from 40-ply stiff laminates, with a stacking sequence $[45/0_2/-45/90]_{4S}$, to give a width of 25 mm. The bolts had a diameter of 6.35 mm. The non-blind fastener was tightened to a torque of 13 N·m. A bending restraint guide provided constraint against secondary bending. Two printed parallel line patterns were bonded on the sides of the joints, as shown in Figure 4. By inspecting photographs taken periodically during the test the relative displacement between the straps at a given load was measured. The results are presented in Figure 5 together with estimates by equation (3), where the good correlation with the blind fasteners indicates that the value of β was close 0.5 for this joint.

Two bolted repair panels were tested under tension loading at room temperature. The parent and doubler laminates were 30-ply unidirectional tape prepreg (IM7/5250-4) with a stacking sequence of $[45/0_2/-45/90]_{3S}$. The dimensions of the panels are shown in Figure 6, which show the panel with and without the repair for clarity. The panels were identical except for the dimensions of the cutout, where one panel used a circular cutout as shown in Figure 6, and the other used a rectangular cutout.

Figure 4: Images of single-bolt joint testing of a blind fastener at (a) 0 N (b) 10.2 kN.

Figure 5: Load displacement data measured using single-bolt lap shear tests.

Figure 6: Dimensions (inches) of bolted repair panels with strain gauge (SG) locations.

The results of a strain survey test for one of these panels are displayed in Figure 7, indicating that the strain at the centre of the doubler was approximately 31% of the strain in the parent laminate away from the repair. This means that the doubler effectively reduced the load going through the cutout region by 31%. Given that the strain concentration factor at the edge of a circular hole was approximately 2.3 for this stiff laminate (as determined by FE analysis), the doubler effectively reduced the predicted strain concentration factor to 1.59. This was close to the experimental value of 1.76, as evident by the values of the strain gauge at the hole edge shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Results of experimental strain survey at room temperature.

Analysis

The experimental results indicated that the bolted doublers carried only a small fraction of the applied load, suggesting a relatively low structural efficiency. The reason for this phenomenon is that the stiffness of the bolted doubler is significantly less than that of the host structure. This load-shedding effect of the bolted doubler can be analysed by the inclusion analogy similar to that employed for analysing bonded repairs. Figure 8 shows the case of single row bolted joint. The problem can be modelled as an inclusion, which has the same extensional stiffness as the bolted joint at the innermost row of bolts as shown on the right in Figure 8. The relative displacement between the two innermost bolts, Δ , due to inclusion stress σ_i is given by,

$$\Delta = (L + 2p) \frac{\sigma_i t_s}{t_d E_d} + 2C \sigma_i w t_s + 2b_c, \quad (4)$$

where C denotes the bolt compliance given by equation (3). The parameter w denotes the effective width (distance between adjacent bolt columns), t_s is the thickness of the skin, t_d is the thickness of the doubler, b_c is the bolt clearance, and L and p are geometry parameters as shown on the right in Figure 8. The modulus of the equivalent inclusion, E_i , is defined as

$$E_i = \frac{L + 2p}{\Delta} \sigma_i. \quad (5)$$

For zero bolt clearance, the modulus of the equivalent inclusion E_i can be explicitly expressed, noting the thickness of the inclusion is taken to be equal to the skin thickness, as

$$E_i = E_d \frac{1}{1 + 2C w t_s E_d / (L + 2p)}. \quad (6)$$

It is clear that as the cutout size L increases, the modulus of the inclusion approaches that of the doubler. However, for small cutouts, the modulus of the equivalent inclusion is significantly less than that of the doubler.

Figure 8: A structural model representing the bolted doubler repair. Left: Inclusion representation. Right: Structural detail of the inclusion.

For non-zero bolt clearance, the modulus of the equivalent inclusion depends on the stress in the doubler; an explicit expression for the inclusion stress can be derived by solving equations (1) and (5), which yields the following expressions for the inclusion modulus and inclusion stress,

$$E_i = E_d \frac{3(L+2p) - 2b_c E_s / \sigma_{applied}}{3(L+2p + 2CE_d t_s w) + 4b_c E_d / \sigma_{applied}}, \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_i = \frac{3(L+2p) - 2b_c E_s / \sigma_{applied}}{(2 + E_s / E_d)(L+2p) + 2Cb_c E_s t_s w} \sigma_{applied}. \quad (8)$$

The low stiffness of the bolted repair implies that the reduction in parent stress near the edge of the cutout is much less than for adhesively bonded repairs of the same thickness. To restore the load carrying capacity to the as-designed level, the repair must be designed to avoid laminate failure at the edge of the cutout in the parent structure.

As an example, Figure 9 shows results for a 30-ply IM7/5250-4 stiff laminate with blind fasteners of diameter $D = 6.35$ mm, at pitch $p = 2.5D$ and effective width of $4D$. The moduli of the laminate in the longitudinal and lateral directions are respectively 77 GPa and 50 GPa, according to laminate theory. It is seen that the bolt clearance has only a minor influence at the applied stress of $\sigma_{applied} = 500$ MPa. The numerical results presented in Figure 9, ($p/d = 2.5$, $w/d = 4$) confirm that the bolted repairs using countersink blind fasteners are much more compliant than the parent structure, especially for cutout sizes two orders of magnitude less than the structure thickness.

The predicted ratios of doubler stress to the applied stress for snug-fit (zero bolt clearance) and clearance fit (clearance $b_c = 0.15$ mm) are presented in Figure 9, together with experimental results. As expected, the percentage of load being transferred into the doubler depends strongly on the cutout size and only weakly on bolt clearance: the larger the cutout the higher the doubler stress. Due to the relatively low bolt stiffness, bolt clearance plays only a minor role. Also shown in Figure 9 are the experimental data from two panels with different cutout dimensions, indicating a reasonable correlation.

These results reveal that the bolted doubler repair is effective only for a very large damage cutout of the order of 100 times the structure's thickness. As seen in Figure 9, the effective modulus of the bolted repair to a 75 mm diameter circular cutout is only about 10% of the parent skin. This means that the stress concentration factor is reduced from a nominal 3 to 2.5, which may result in composite failure at the cutout edge. Adding more rows of bolts will only achieve moderate improvement. To further reduce the stress in the parent structure, the shape of the cutout must be optimised; this will be investigated in future work.

Figure 9: Influence of cutout size on repair efficiency. Left: Stiffness. Right: Stress.

Figure 10: Influence of repair thickness on stress concentration at cutout.

Further evidence of the low reinforcement efficiency of bolted repairs is presented in Figure 10. The FE results in this figure were generated by modelling the parent structure and doubler as separate shell element layers, connected with spring-like elements at the bolt locations. The spring stiffness was taken from single-lap shear tests, such as those

shown in Figure 5. The analytical curve for the single plate is the classic elasticity solution for stress away from a circular hole in an isotropic plate, whilst the “welded doubler” solution is the single plate curve divided by 2 to account for a doubler of equal thickness to the parent. While a rigidly welded doubler of matching property reduces the stress concentration factor of a circular hole from 3.0 to 1.5, the bolted doublers of various thickness ratios could only lower the stress concentration factor to 2.23.

CONCLUSIONS

A significant load-bypass effect has been found around bolted doubler repairs to through-thickness damage, while adhesively bonded scarf repairs using low-stiffness repairs would exhibit a moderate load-bypass. Rapid analysis methods have been developed to quantify the level of load-bypass, and have been supported with FE analyses. The results revealed that reducing the stiffness of an adhesively bonded scarf repair would not yield any significant reductions in adhesive stresses. For bolted doubler repairs, the low stiffness of the bolted connection has been found to result in poor structural efficiency, which must be taken into account in designing mechanically fastened repairs to avoid premature failure of the host structure at the cutout area.

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